

seedlings were transplanted at 15-cm spacing. Water rose at 2-3 cm/d to a maximum water depth of 112 cm. Neither species had superior yield, but *O. glaberrima* showed more vigorous vegetative growth. □

Varietal differences in milled quality of rice harvested at different maturities

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Rice varieties differ in grain form, milling outturn, and market price. Harvesting at different stages of maturity also affects head rice outturn and grain breakage.

Preliminary farm surveys during the 1986 crop season showed that most farmers in the Upper Nun Valley do not follow recommended practices for time of harvest. Many leave their crops in the field after maturity, harvesting when they have time. Rice harvested at different maturity stages mills out with high percentage brokens and very low percentage head rice.

We grew four promising varieties and lines in nonreplicated large plots (500 m²) at Bamunka Rice Research Station, Ndop Plain, and harvested 100 m² subplots at intervals of 5 d, from 35 d after heading (DH) to 60 DH. The yields (20-40 kg rough rice/sample) were sun-dried to about 12-14% moisture, hulled, and polished using a Satake rubber roll rice mill (model SB 100). Percentages brown rice, head rice, broken rice, and marketable rice were taken for each sample. (Head rice is defined as whole milled rice, marketable rice as grains 50-100% as long as whole milled rice.) Estimated 1,000-grain weights of rough rice and brown rice also were noted for each harvest date.

Total brown and clean milled rice varied with varieties, from 73.8 to 81.7% brown rice and 63.5 to 71.3% clean milled rice, but were not markedly affected by harvest date (see table).

Effect of harvesting rice at different stages of maturity on milling outturns. Ndop Plain, Cameroon, 1987 wet season.

Variety or line	Harvest date (DH) ^a	Rough rice moisture at harvest (%)	Percent of rough rice			
			Brown rice	Clean rice	Head ^b rice	Marketable rice ^c
RNR29692	35	27.6	73.8	66.4	58.7	64.1
	40	27.1	75.5	69.5	58.3	67.6
	45	22.0	79.3	68.5	57.5	65.6
	50	20.0	79.0	65.8	35.6	60.4
	55	18.0	81.0	69.1	46.9	65.8
IR7167-33-2-3	40	30.4	81.3	71.1	42.1	68.5
	45	26.5	77.7	71.3	30.0	66.7
	50	24.5	77.1	67.5	19.9	61.6
	55	22.5	79.5	66.2	8.7	55.9
	60	12.8	80.1	71.2	10.0	63.0
B29838-SR-51-2-1	40	29.4	80.5	63.5	23.2	53.2
	45	26.5	79.2	68.9	33.5	59.0
	50	24.4	75.7	64.9	13.8	50.3
	55	22.5	78.6	67.8	14.5	52.3
	60	14.1	77.7	65.5	5.1	45.0
B2161-C-MR-57-1-3-1	35	30.9	75.7	62.7	16.5	40.2
	40	29.4	74.0	66.2	13.1	51.0
	45	26.5	77.4	67.0	19.2	56.8
	50	24.5	81.2	63.2	14.3	46.5
	55	18.7	77.1	68.7	7.1	55.2
60	11.5	81.7	67.3	3.7	44.9	

^a DH = days after heading. ^b Head rice = % whole milled rice. ^c marketable rice = 50% or more than the length of whole milled rice.

RNR29692 had the highest (51.4%) and B2161-C-MR-57-1-3-1 the lowest (12.3%) head rice.

Grain maturity stage profoundly affected percentage brokens. Harvest more than 45 DH resulted in very high percentage brokens.

Extremely high, percentage brokens in all varieties (except RNR29692) harvested 40 DH and later tend to limit their adaptability as commercial varieties.

RNR29692 yielded higher than IR7167-33-2-3 at Ndop Plain. Both lines have medium-long grain with high amylose content (28.3%); B2161-C-MR-57-1-3-1 and B29838-SR-51-2-1 have medium-long grain with intermediate amylose content (23.7%). Because of its high head rice percentage, RNR29692 is under consideration for release as a commercial variety, subject to local consumer acceptance and other qualities. □

Effect on yield of cutting deepwater rice for herbage

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During the 1988 wet season, we cut leaves of variety CN705-18 (CN645/ Mahsuri) at different growth stages. The first cutting of the 10 May direct seeded crop was done 110 d after seeding in two plots. A second cutting was done 130 d after seeding

(immediately before panicle initiation) in only one plot. Water level at cutting was 50-60 cm (maximum water level 90 cm was in late June). Only leaves above the water were cut, leaving 5 cm of leaves intact.

Foliage yield, grain yield, and yield components were measured. The first cut in plot A produced 3.8 t green leaves/ha and in plot B, 3.6 t green leaves/ha. The second cut in plot B only 20 d after the first cut produced 3.4 t green leaves/ha (Table 1). Grain yields in single cut and uncut crops were